

The Influence of Website Quality on Customer E-Satisfaction in Low Cost Airline

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Abstract : The evolution of customer behavior in purchasing products or services through the Internet leads to airline companies engaging in the e-ticketing process in order to maintain their business. A well-designed website is vitally significant for the airline companies to provide effective communication, support, and competitive advantage. This study was conducted to identify the dimensions of website quality for low cost airline and to investigate the relationship between the website quality and customer e-satisfaction at low cost airline. A total of 381 responses were conveniently collected among local passengers at Low Cost Carrier Terminal, Kuala Lumpur via questionnaire distribution. This study found that the five determinant factors of website quality for AirAsia were Information Content, Navigation, Responsiveness, Personalization, and Security and Privacy. The results of this study revealed that there is a positive relationship between the five dimensions of website quality and customer e-satisfaction, and also information content was the most significant contributor to customer e-satisfaction.

Keywords : website quality, customer e-satisfaction, low cost airline, e-ticketing

Conference Title : ICHTMM 2014 : International Conference on Hospitality, Tourism Marketing and Management

Conference Location : Cape Town, South Africa

Conference Dates : November 06-07, 2014